

USING SONGS AND MUSIC IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO TEENAGE AND ADULT LEARNERS

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Annotation. This article focuses the significance of utilizing songs and music in teaching foreign language to teenage and adult learners. Throughout this way, it is highlighted that the language skills of learners improve in noticeably level.

Key words and expression: Rhyme, rhythm, phonetic forecast, grammar rules, fluency, lyrics, phonetic script, pronunciation.

Why do EFL teachers apply music to teenage and adult learners in teaching foreign languages? Songs offer teens learning English useful listening practice, but they do so differently. Music can express emotions and tell stories. Music may affect the mood or set the setting. A song can be used to start or close a lesson or to focus an entire session on its message and the singer or band that made it. The rhyme and rhythm of songs are excellent for practicing pronunciation when learning a new language. Songs can be used to assist students "notice" language use, infer words' or phrases' meanings from context, and launch speaking or writing exercises since they frequently repeat vocabulary or grammar structures.

All of these abilities are beneficial for raising students' overall English proficiency as well as for exam preparation. Understanding songs in English can inspire students, who frequently enjoy doing so.

Considerations: Musical taste - teenagers will have a very distinct sense of the music they enjoy and detest! Ask them, and employ a variety of music in your classes (maybe as a class survey).¹

The appropriateness of the songs, videos, and advertisements should be determined before the class by carefully reading and listening to the lyrics and watching the entire video. Be cautious of songs and films that may include inappropriate adverts that are hosted on websites. Simply play the audio if necessary rather than the video.

When choosing a song, keep in mind that numerous emotions might be evoked by listening to music. Also, some of your students may find the topics of some songs to be sensitive.

Verify that the lyrics are appropriate for the song version you are using. Live performances or covers could differ slightly.

Do these things before, during, and after song listening

Phonetic forecast

Choose a song whose lyrics rhyme. Encourage students to generate lists of rhymes in pairs using words from the ends of some of the lines. Next students listen and mark the words they hear on their lists.

Instead, kids can jot down the words on pieces of paper and select the ones they hear. You can use the phonemic script to help students find rhyming words if they are familiar with it.

¹ Cambridgeenglish.org.Cambridge University Press & Assessment , by Cambridge English. Aug.2020 .

In the Speaking section of their Cambridge English Qualification, students are evaluated on a number of aspects, including pronunciation. Songs are a fun way to highlight and practice pronunciation.

Benefits of Using Music to Teach English

A few benefits of using songs in ESL lessons are as follows:

Boost student motivation, reinforce grammar rules, improve vocabulary and pronunciation, make learning easier by helping students memorize patterns, and increase fluency.

The Drawbacks of Using Music to Teach English

Songs could have the following issues:

Slang or ungrammatical sentences (he don't...), and have a difficult vocabulary that even upper intermediate students will not be able to understand. They can also be very fast for ESL learners.

Using Songs: Addressing the Difficulties

If a song's tempo makes it difficult for ESL students to finish the listening exercises, play the song at least three times and pause it at various verses to give them time to finish the job.

Singing the song more slowly before checking the answers is another option for this problem.²

Always warn listeners that songs might not be sung with the proper pronunciation or grammar. You might also ask them to listen to the music and correct any incorrect grammar or usage with Standard English as they hear it.

When dealing with vocabulary issues, you can get ready for them by pre-teaching the new terms and asking the kids to use them to construct sentences or stories, which could also be a way for them to speculate on the song's theme.

Songs and Games for Fun English Teaching

Here are some suggestions for using songs in your classes. You have to add words or phrases, construct questions, or rework portions of the songs for the majority of activities. "Fill in the Gaps" is the song activity that is used the most frequently. As long as you don't overuse it, it's a good ESL activity. Otherwise, your students might grow weary of participating in the same activity for each song they hear. Moreover, be careful to pick the appropriate term to omit so they can fill in the blanks. If you've chosen a song to review a certain grammar concept and it involves a recurring pattern, such as conditionals, you should remove the verbs from the main clause or the if-clause so that the conditional structure is the major focus. While instructing a beginner's class, you should either omit fewer terms or place the words in a box from which the students can select.

In conclusion, songs are a great way for students to relax and enjoy themselves while learning English. Many ESL instructors believe that utilizing songs in the classroom is only appropriate for young students or as a way to inspire teenagers. Songs can help adults learn just as well as children, even though kids learn best by doing and singing, and teens love learning the words to their favorite songs or bands.

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